

Triterpenoids: XXXII. The Structure of Lantic Acid-A New Triterpene from *Lantana camara*

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In our previous communications the isolation of a new triterpene, lantanolic acid, from the leaves of *Lantana camara* was reported¹ and its structure (I) was elucidated². It has now been possible to isolate two other triterpene acids from the same source. One of these acids was isolated as its methyl ester, $C_{31}H_{48}O_3$, m.p. 191-92°, [α]_D +83° (Pyridine) (M^+ 468), and was identified as 3-keto methyl ursolate by comparison of mixed melting point with an authentic sample (m.p. 191-93°) prepared by Sarett oxidation of methyl ursolate.

The other acid, $C_{30}H_{46}O_4$, m.p. 256-59°, [α]_D³⁵ +153° (CHCl₃), has been found to be a new triterpene and named as lantic acid (IIa). It formed a methyl ester (IIb), $C_{31}H_{48}O_4$, 1H₂O (M^+ 484), m.p. 130-32°, [α]_D³⁷ +124° (CHCl₃); λ_{max} 207 m μ (log ϵ 3.8; trisubstituted double bond), which showed pale yellow colour with tetranitromethane. Methyl lantate, like methyl lantanolate, formed the ketal (IIc), $C_{32}H_{50}O_4$ (M^+ 498), m.p. 153-55°, on refluxing with methanolic sulphuric acid which gave back methyl lantate on treatment with dilute hydrochloric acid in tetrahydrofuran. Methyl lantate on treatment with KBH₄ gave the diol (IIIa), $C_{31}H_{50}O_4$, m.p. 216-18°, which on oxidation with CrO₃-pyridine complex yielded the keto aldehyde (IIIb), $C_{31}H_{46}O_4$, m.p. 170-75°. This product, unlike methyl lantate (IIb), gave positive Zimmermann colour test for a 3-keto group³, thus locating a secondary hydroxyl group at C-3 in the diol. As this secondary hydroxyl group in the diol is formed by the reduction of the potential keto group in methyl lantate, the latter must be located at C-3 position. Methyl lantate on Wolff-Kishner reduction followed by diazomethane treatment, furnished the product (IIIc), $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$, m.p. 160-62° (M^+ 470), which contains a free primary hydroxyl group, as evident from the peak at m/e 439 (M-31; M-CH₂OH) in its mass spectrum. The product (IIIc) on oxidation with CrO₃-pyridine complex furnished the aldehyde (IIId), $C_{31}H_{48}O_3$, m.p. 137-40°, which on Wolff-Kishner reduction under anhydrous condition⁴ followed by diazomethane treatment yielded a product (IV), $C_{31}H_{50}O_2$, m.p. 118-119°. This was identified as 3-deoxy methyl ursolate (IV) by t.l.c.,

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mixed m.p. and i.r. spectra. As the potential 3-keto group and the hydroxymethylene group in lantic acid form parts of a hemi-ketal system, the hydroxymethylene group could be placed only at C-4 or C-10. The former position was however overruled because methyl lantate did not undergo retroaldolization in presence of alkali (cf. icterogenin⁴ and methyl hederagone).

The n.m.r. spectrum (60 Mc, $CDCl_3$) of methyl lantate showed two sharp singlets at 3.59 (3H, $COOCH_3$) and 1.71 δ (1H, OH ; disappeared on exchange with D_2O). A triplet at 5.27 δ (1H) was due to the C-12 vinyl proton. The two nonequivalent methylene protons of the hemi-ketal ring appeared as pair of doublets centred at 4.24 and 3.88 δ ($J=8.5$ c.p.s.) which were further splitted ($J=2.5$ and 1 c. p. s., respectively) by long range coupling with one of the C-1 protons.

The mass spectrum of methyl lantate showed the molecular ion at m/e 484 and the r.d.a. fragment at m/e 262 (ion a) which clearly showed the absence of any other oxygen function in ring C, D and E of lantic acid except the carboxyl group.

On the basis of the evidences presented so far the structure and stereochemistry of lantic acid may be represented as (IIa).

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